

Molar Excess Volumes and Excess Isentropic Compressibilities of Ternary Mixtures Containing 2-Pyrrolidinone

Jaibir S. Yadav, Dimple, and Vinod K. Sharma

Abstract—Molar excess Volumes, V_{ijk}^E and speeds of sound, u_{ijk} of 2-pyrrolidinone (i) + benzene or toluene (j) + ethanol (k) ternary mixture have been measured as a function of composition at 308.15 K. The observed speeds of sound data have been utilized to determine excess isentropic compressibilities, $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ of ternary (i + j + k) mixtures. Molar excess volumes, V_{ijk}^E and excess isentropic compressibilities, $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ data have fitted to the Redlich-Kister equation to calculate ternary adjustable parameters and standard deviations. The Moelywn-Huggins concept (Huggins in Polymer 12: 389-399, 1971) of connectivity between the surfaces of the constituents of binary mixtures has been extended to ternary mixtures (using the concept of a connectivity parameter of third degree of molecules, $^3\xi$, which inturn depends on its topology) to obtain an expression that describes well the measured V_{ijk}^E and $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ data.

Keywords—Connectivity parameter of third degree, $^3\xi$, Excess isentropic compressibilities, $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$, Interaction energy parameter, χ , Molar excess volumes, V_{ijk}^E , Speeds of sound, u_{ijk} .

I. INTRODUCTION

EVER since the suggestion that constitutional formula of a molecule is a special kind of graph [1] called molecular graph and a very good correlation have been observed [2-6] between topological index [7] of a molecule and its physico-chemical properties. The characterization of the mixtures through their topological investigations [8-10] has proved to be a reliable way to extract information about the structure of components of mixtures in pure and mixed state and molecular interactions operating among the constituents of mixtures. Further topological investigations have been successfully employed to determine molar excess volumes, molar excess enthalpies, excess isentropic compressibilities of binary [11-14] and ternary [15-17] mixtures. Cyclic amides are of great interest because the nitrogen and carbon atoms of peptide bond are linked by a ring composed of methyl groups.

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These compounds have generated special interest because the amide group is a structural part of peptides, polypeptides and proteins. IR spectroscopic and thermodynamic studies of 2-pyrrolidinone + benzene or toluene or o- or p- or m-xylene (j) binary mixtures have revealed [18-20] that 2-pyrrolidinone is a self associated molecular entity (mixture of cyclic and open dimer). As a continuation and extension of our studies on the thermodynamic properties of 2-pyrrolidinone (i) + benzene or toluene or o- or p- or m-xylene (j) mixture, we report here molar volumes, V_{ijk}^E , speeds of sound, u_{ijk} data for 2-pyrrolidinone (i) + benzene or toluene (j) + ethanol (k) ternary mixtures at 308.15 K. An attempt has also been made to develop an expression by employing topology of the constituents of mixtures that describes well molar excess volumes, V_{ijk}^E and excess isentropic compressibility, $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ of these ternary mixtures.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

A. Materials

2-Pyrrolidinone (**2-Py**) (Fluka), benzene, toluene and absolute ethanol (AR Grade) were purified by standard methods [21].

B. Methods

The purities of the purified liquids were checked by measuring their densities with a pycnometer at 298.15 ± 0.01 K and the resulting densities (reported in Table I) agreed to within ± 0.05 kgm^{-3} of their corresponding literature values [21].

Molar excess volumes, V_{ijk}^E for ternary mixtures were measured in a dilatometer in the manner described elsewhere [22]. The dilatometer had three limbs for three components. The change in liquid level of dilatometer capillary was measured with a cathetometer that could read to ± 0.001 cm. The temperature of the water thermostat was controlled to better than ± 0.01 K by means of toluene regulator. The uncertainty in the measured V_{ijk}^E values is ± 0.5 percent.

The speed of sound at frequency 2MHz was determined using a quartz crystal interferometer (Model-M 80, Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi, India). The measuring cell was a specially designed double walled cell in which water was circulated to maintain the temperature at 308.15 ± 0.01 K. The speed of sound values for the purified liquids at $298.15 \pm$

0.01K (recorded in Table I) compare well with their corresponding experimental values [23-27]. The uncertainty in the measured speed of sound measurements is ± 1 m/sec.

TABLE I

COMPARISON OF DENSITIES, ρ , AND SPEEDS OF SOUND, u , OF PURE LIQUIDS WITH THEIR LITERATURE VALUES AT 298.15 K.

Liquid	ρ (kg. m ⁻³)		u (ms ⁻¹)	
	Exptl.	Lit.	Exptl.	Lit.
2-pyrrolidinone	1107.26	1107.22 ²³	1603.0 ^a	1603.1 ^{a24}
Benzene	873.62	873.60 ²¹	1298.2	1298.9 ²⁵
Toluene	862.23	862.19 ²¹	1304.6	1304.0 ²⁶
Ethanol	785.08	785.93 ²¹	1112.0	1109.05 ²⁷

^aVALUE AT 308.15 K

III. RESULTS

Molar excess volumes, V_{ijk}^E , and speeds of sound, u_{ijk} , data of **2-Py** (i) + benzene (j) + ethanol (k) ternary mixtures as a function of composition at 308.15 K are recorded in Tables II and III respectively. The isentropic compressibilities, $(\kappa_S)_{ijk}$ for ternary mixtures were determined using the expression:

$$(\kappa_S)_{ijk} = (\rho_{ijk} u_{ijk}^2)^{-1} \quad (1)$$

The densities, ρ_{ijk} of ternary mixtures were calculated from their experimental molar excess volumes data using the Equation (2)

$$V_{ijk}^E = \sum_{i=1}^k x_i M_i (\rho_{ijk})^{-1} - \sum_{i=1}^k x_i M_i (\rho_i)^{-1} \quad (2)$$

where x_i , M_i and ρ_i are the mole fraction, molar mass and density respectively of component (i) in (i + j + k) ternary mixtures.

Excess isentropic compressibilities, $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ were evaluated using Equation (3)

$$(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk} = (\kappa_S)_{ijk} - \kappa_S^{id} \quad (3)$$

κ_S^{id} was obtained according to Benson and Kiyohara [28]

$$\kappa_S^{id} = \sum_i^{jork} \phi_i \left[\kappa_{S,i} + \frac{TV_i \alpha_i^2}{C_{p,i}} \right] - T \left(\sum_i^{jork} x_i V_i \right) \frac{\left(\sum_i^{jork} \phi_i \alpha_i \right)^2}{\left(\sum_i^{jork} x_i C_{p,i} \right)} \quad (4)$$

where ϕ_i is the volume fraction of component (i) in the mixture referred to as the unmixed state, x_i is the corresponding mole fraction, T is the absolute temperature, and $\kappa_{S,i}$, V_i , α_i and $C_{p,i}$ are the isentropic compressibility, molar volume, thermal expansion coefficient, and molar heat capacity of the pure component (i), respectively. The values of α and $C_{p,i}$ were taken from literature [29]. α value for **2-Py**

was evaluated in the same manner as suggested by Hilderbrand [30]. The resulting $(\kappa_S)_{ijk}$ and $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ values for the studied (i + j + k) ternary mixtures are recorded in Table III and V_{ijk}^E , $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ values are plotted in Figs. 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively.

V_{ijk}^E and $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ values for ternary mixtures were fitted to Redlich-Kister Equation (5)

$$X_{ijk}^E (X=V \text{ or } \kappa_S) = x_i x_j \left[\sum_{n=0}^2 X_{ij}^{(n)} (x_i - x_j)^n \right] + x_j x_k \left[\sum_{n=0}^2 X_{jk}^{(n)} (x_j - x_k)^n \right] + x_i x_k \left[\sum_{n=0}^2 X_{ik}^{(n)} (x_k - x_i)^n \right] + x_i x_j x_k \left[\sum_{n=0}^2 X_{ijk}^{(n)} (x_i - x_j)^n (x_j - x_k)^n (x_k - x_i)^n \right] \quad (5)$$

where x_i and x_j are the mole fractions of i^{th} and j^{th} components of (i + j + k) ternary mixture; $X_{ij}^{(n)}$ ($n=0-2$) etc. ($X=V$ or κ_S) are the parameters characteristic of (i+j), (j+k) and (i+k) binary mixtures and have been taken from literature [20,31,32]. $X_{ijk}^{(n)}$ ($X=V$ or κ_S) parameters were determined by fitting X_{ijk}^E data to Equation (6) by the least-squares method and

$$\begin{bmatrix} X_{ijk}^E - x_i x_j \left[\sum_{n=0}^2 X_{ij}^{(n)} (x_i - x_j)^n \right] \\ - x_j x_k \left[\sum_{n=0}^2 X_{jk}^{(n)} (x_j - x_k)^n \right] \\ - x_k x_i \left[\sum_{n=0}^2 X_{ik}^{(n)} (x_k - x_i)^n \right] \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_i x_j x_k \\ x_i x_j x_k \\ x_i x_j x_k \end{bmatrix}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{n=0}^2 X_{ijk}^{(n)} (x_i - x_j)^n (x_j - x_k)^n (x_k - x_i)^n \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

are recorded along with their standard deviations, $\sigma (X_{ijk}^E)$ ($X=V$ or κ_S) defined by

$$\sigma (X_{ijk}^E) = [\sum (X_{ijk}^E(\text{exptl}) - X_{ijk}^E(\text{Calc.Equation(4)})^2 / (m - p)]^{0.5}$$

{where m, n are the number of data points and adjustable parameters in Equation (5)} in Tables II and III respectively.

TABLE II

COMPARISON OF MEASURED, V_{ijk}^E VALUES FOR THE VARIOUS (i+j+k) TERNARY MIXTURES EVALUATED FROM GRAPH THEORY WITH THEIR CORRESPONDING EXPERIMENTAL VALUES; ALSO INCLUDED ARE THE VARIOUS PARAMETERS $V_{ijk}^{(n)}$ ($n=0-2$) ALONG WITH THEIR STANDARD DEVIATION, $\sigma (V_{ijk}^E)$, INTERACTION PARAMETERS χ^* , χ_{ij} ETC. AND CONNECTIVITY PARAMETERS OF THIRD DEGREE, ${}^3\zeta_i$ ($i=i-k$)

x_i	x_j	V_{ijk}^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	
		Exptl	Graph
2-pyrrolidinone (i) +benzene (j) + ethanol (k)			
0.1058	0.7933	-0.121	-0.100
0.1214	0.6976	-0.100	-0.115
0.2083	0.3519	-0.243	-0.242
0.2455	0.4351	-0.269	-0.277
0.2806	0.1970	-0.390	-0.388

0.3477	0.3556	-0.392	-0.380
0.4078	0.3679	-0.398	-0.397
0.4624	0.2948	-0.455	-0.438
0.5326	0.1630	-0.497	-0.497
0.5872	0.1713	-0.474	-0.470
0.6615	0.2302	-0.394	-0.391
0.7106	0.1382	-0.388	-0.394
0.7500	0.0703	-0.339	-0.382
0.8405	0.0721	-0.237	-0.261
0.8801	0.0656	-0.188	-0.204

$$V_{ijk}^{(0)} = -0.513; V_{ijk}^{(1)} = 19.431; V_{ijk}^{(2)} = 181.875;$$

$$\sigma(V_{ijk}^E) = 0.003$$

$$({}^3\xi_i) = 1.001; ({}^3\xi_j) = 0.666; ({}^3\xi_k) = 1.503$$

$$\chi^* = -1.100; \chi'_{ij} = -0.317; \chi'_{jk} = 0.979; \chi'_{ik} = -1.058$$

Fig. 1 Molar excess volumes, V^E for 2-pyrrolidinone (i) + benzene (j) + ethanol (k) ternary mixture at 308.15 K

2-pyrrolidinone (i) +toluene (j) + ethanol (k)

0.0514	0.9290	-0.066	-0.159
0.1159	0.7845	-0.163	-0.276
0.2421	0.4736	-0.356	-0.355
0.3283	.02435	-0.333	-0.336
0.3892	0.3584	-0.514	-0.515
0.4268	0.4038	-0.609	-0.624
0.5178	0.2826	-0.554	-0.557
0.5799	0.1663	-0.428	-0.427
0.6243	0.2258	-0.530	-0.533
0.6976	0.0816	-0.340	-0.308
0.7655	0.1069	-0.343	-0.331
0.8588	0.452	-0.203	-0.180
0.8898	0.0629	-0.198	-0.164
0.9426	0.0311	-0.105	-0.108

$$V_{ijk}^{(0)} = 1.320; V_{ijk}^{(1)} = -46.051; V_{ijk}^{(2)} = 22.942;$$

$$\sigma(V_{ijk}^E) = 0.004$$

$$({}^3\xi_i) = 1.001; ({}^3\xi_j) = 0.840; ({}^3\xi_k) = 1.503$$

$$\chi^* = -1.137; \chi'_{ij} = -1.778; \chi'_{jk} = 1.796; \chi'_{ik} = -0.449$$

$V_{ijk}^{(n)}$ ($n = 0-2$) and $\sigma(V_{ijk}^E)$ are in $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$
 χ^* and χ'_{ij} etc. are in $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$

Fig. 2 Molar excess volumes, V^E for 2-pyrrolidinone (i) + toluene (j) + ethanol (k) ternary mixture at 308.15 K

TABLE III

SPEEDS OF SOUND, U_{ijk} , ISENTROPIC COMPRESSIBILITIES, $(\kappa_S)_{ijk}$, EXCESS ISENTROPIC COMPRESSIBILITIES, $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ FOR THE VARIOUS (i+j+k) TERNARY MIXTURES AS A FUNCTION OF COMPOSITION, x_i , MOLE FRACTION OF COMPONENT (i) AT 308.15 K WITH $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ VALUES EVALUATED FROM GRAPH THEORY ALSO INCLUDED ARE VARIOUS PARAMETERS $(\kappa_S^{(n)})_{ijk}$ (n = 0-2) ALONG WITH THEIR STANDARD DEVIATION, $\sigma(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$, THE INTERACTION PARAMETERS χ'_{ij} , χ'_{ji} *ETC AND $(^3\xi_i)$ (i = i - k)

x_i	x_j	U_{ijk} (ms^{-1})	$(\kappa_S)_{ijk}$ (Tpa^{-1})	$(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ (Tpa^{-1})	
				Exptl.	Graph
2-pyrrolidinone (i) +benzene (j) + ethanol (k)					
0.0982	0.1092	1201	836.2	-75.7	-69.4
0.1526	0.1529	1233	770.6	-84.9	-83.9
0.2465	0.1712	1274	692.7	-89.3	-89.5
0.3018	0.6178	1327	613.1	-30.6	-30.1
0.3440	0.0830	1315	630.1	-108.4	-78.5
0.3925	0.5038	1353	576.7	-37.9	-37.7
0.4510	0.1324	1351	573.7	-80.6	-80.2
0.5022	0.4118	1395	527.5	-42.3	-35.9
0.6378	0.0699	1431	484.7	-64.7	-59.7
0.7112	0.1368	1472	448.9	-46.8	-44.9
0.7331	0.2113	1493	434.2	-38.5	-27.1
0.8316	0.0612	1530	403.6	-34.7	-30.1
0.8748	0.0310	1550	389.2	-29.2	-23.6
$(\kappa_S^{(0)})_{ijk} = -3.3$, $(\kappa_S^{(1)})_{ijk} = 48.9$, $(\kappa_S^{(2)})_{ijk} = 274.1$, $\sigma(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk} = 0.1 Tpa^{-1}$ $(^3\xi_i) = 1.001$; $(^3\xi_j) = 0.666$; $(^3\xi_k) = 2.000$ $\chi^* = -32.5$; $\chi'_{ij} = -26.7$; $\chi'_{jk} = -346.1$; $\chi'_{ik} = -89.3$					
2-pyrrolidinone (i) + toluene (j) + ethanol (k)					
0.0582	0.9018	1276	712.4	-14.1	-2.9
0.0910	0.0605	1195	851.9	-81.6	-73.3
0.1282	0.7892	1288	689.1	-23.8	-11.9
0.1646	0.0298	1236	771.8	-116.2	-107.0
0.2062	0.0859	1260	726.4	-109.7	-109.9
0.3080	0.6142	1337	611.1	-43.8	-43.5
0.3557	0.0638	1321	624.0	-112.2	-112.6

0.4140	0.5088	1364	571.2	-46.5	-63.9
0.4451	0.0319	1361	569.8	-111.8	-99.9
0.5643	0.0674	1394	523.7	-74.9	-74.4
0.7605	0.0346	1485	436.4	-47.5	-32.7
0.8612	0.0726	1531	402.1	-25.1	-40.2
0.9263	0.0413	1565	378.3	-15.2	-25.0

$(\kappa_S^{(0)})_{ijk} = -2.0$, $(\kappa_S^{(1)})_{ijk} = -18.1$, $(\kappa_S^{(2)})_{ijk} = -33.9$,
 $\sigma(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk} = 0.1 Tpa^{-1}$
 $(^3\xi_i) = 1.101$; $(^3\xi_j) = 0.84$; $(^3\xi_k) = 2.000$
 $\chi^* = -582.2$; $\chi'_{ij} = -9.5$; $\chi'_{jk} = -1.7$; $\chi'_{ik} = 20.8$

$\kappa_S^{(n)}_{ijk}$ (n=0-2) and $\sigma(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ are in Tpa^{-1}
 χ^* , χ'_{ij} etc. are in Tpa^{-1}

IV. DISCUSSION

We are unaware of any published V^E_{ijk} and $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ data of the studied (i + j + k) mixtures at 308.15 K with which to compare our results. V^E_{ijk} and $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ values for **2-Py** (i) + benzene or toluene (j) + ethanol (k) mixtures are negative over entire composition range.

A. Graph Theory and Results

An analysis of molar excess volumes, V^E and molar excess enthalpies, H^E data of **2-Py** (i) + benzene or toluene or ethanol (j) binary mixtures have revealed [20,31] that (i) while **2-Py** (i) and ethanol exists as a mixture of open and cyclic dimer; benzene or toluene exist as a monomer. Analysis of V^E and H^E data of **2-Py** (i) + benzene or toluene (j) mixtures in terms of Graph theory have suggested that these binary mixtures are characterized by interactions between π -electron spilling over nitrogen and oxygen atoms of **2-Py** (i) and π -electron cloud of aromatic ring of benzene or toluene to form 1:1 molecular complex. The thermodynamic properties, X^E ($X = H$ or κ_S) for these binary mixtures were expressed by Equation (7)

$$X^E (X = V \text{ or } H) = \frac{x_i x_j (^3\xi_i / ^3\xi_j)}{x_i + x_j (^3\xi_i / ^3\xi_j)} [(1 + x_i)\chi'_{ij} + x_j \chi'_{12}] \quad (7)$$

Further, thermo dynamical investigations of **2-Py** (i) + ethanol (j) mixtures in terms of Graph theory suggests that studied mixtures are characterized by interactions between hydrogen and oxygen atoms of **2-Py** (i) and oxygen, hydrogen atoms of ethanol (j). Thermodynamic properties, X^E ($X = H$ or κ_S) for **2-Py** (i) + ethanol (j) mixtures were then expressed by Equation (8)

$$X^E (X = V \text{ or } H) = [(1 + x_j)\chi'_{ij} + 2x_i \chi^*] \quad (8)$$

Fig. 3 Excess isentropic compressibilities, κ_S^E for 2-pyrrolidinone (i) + benzene (j) + ethanol (k) ternary mixture at 308.15 K

Fig. 4 Excess isentropic compressibilities, κ_S^E for 2-pyrrolidinone (i) + toluene (j) + ethanol (k) ternary mixture at 308.15 K

where χ_{ij} , χ_{12} etc. are the molar volume and enthalpy interaction parameters unlike i-j contacts and specific interaction between (i) and (j) components of (i + j) binary mixtures. H^E and V^E data predicted for these (i+j) binary mixtures {via Equation (7) and (8)} were in good agreement with their corresponding experimental values, which in turn lends additional support to the assumptions made in deriving Equations (7) and (8).

If a third component like ethanol is added to **2-Py** (i) + benzene or toluene (j) binary mixtures, then **2-Py** (i) +

benzene or toluene (j) + ethanol (k) ternary mixtures formation may be assumed to involve processes (1) the establishment of (a) i_n-j , (b) $j-k_n$ and i_n-k_n unlike contacts, (2) formation of unlike contacts would then depolymerize i_n and k_n to form their respective monomers, and (3) specific interaction between i, j and k contacts to form i : j, j : k molecular entities. If χ'_{ij} , χ'_{jk} and χ'_{ik} are the molar volume and molar compressibility interaction parameters of unlike (i-j), (j-k) and (i-k) contacts, then change in molar properties, X^E ($X = V$ or κ_S) due to processes 1{(a)-(c)} can be expressed by relation [33-35]:

$$\Delta X_1 = \left[\frac{x_i x_j v_j}{\sum x_i v_i} \right] \chi'_{ij} + \left[\frac{x_j x_k v_k}{\sum x_j v_j} \right] \chi'_{jk} + \left[\frac{x_k x_i v_i}{\sum x_k v_k} \right] \chi'_{ik} \quad (9)$$

where v_i etc is the molar volume of component (i).

Further, if χ''_{ii} , χ''_{kk} , χ''_{12} , χ''_{12} and χ''_{12} are molar volume and compressibility interaction parameter for i-i, k-k like contacts and specific interactions (leading to the formation of i : j, j : k and i : k molecular entities), then change in molar properties, ΔX ($X = V$ or κ_S) due to processes (2) [ΔX_2 , ΔX_3] and (3) [ΔX_4 - ΔX_6] would be expressed [33-35] as

$$\Delta X_2 = x_i^2 x_j v_j \chi''_{ii} / \sum x_i v_i \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta X_3 = x_i x_k v_k \chi''_{kk} / \sum x_i v_i \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta X_4 = x_i x_j^2 v_j \chi''_{12} / \sum x_i v_i \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta X_5 = x_j x_k^2 v_k \chi''_{12} / \sum x_j v_j \quad (13)$$

$$\Delta X_6 = x_k x_i^2 v_i \chi''_{12} / \sum x_k v_k \quad (14)$$

The overall changes in thermodynamic property, X^E ($X = V$ or κ_S) due to processes 1(a)-(c), 2 and 3 then can be expressed by Equation (15)

$$X^E = \sum_{i=1}^6 \Delta X_i = \left[\frac{x_i x_j v_j}{\sum_{i=1}^j x_i v_i} \right] [\chi'_{ij} + x_i \chi''_{ii} + x_j \chi''_{12}] + \left[\frac{x_j x_k v_k}{\sum_{j=1}^k x_j v_j} \right] [\chi'_{jk} + x_k \chi''_{12}] + \left[\frac{x_i x_k v_i}{\sum_{k=1}^i x_k v_k} \right] [x_k + x_i \chi''_{12} + x_k \chi''_{kk}] \quad (15)$$

Because $v_j / v_i = {}^3 \xi_i / {}^3 \xi_j$ [36]; Equation (15) reduces to Equation (16)

$$X^E = \sum_{i=1}^6 \Delta X_i = \left[\frac{x_i x_j \left(\frac{3\xi_i}{3\xi_j} \frac{3\xi_j}{3\xi_i} \right)}{x_i + x_j \left(\frac{3\xi_i}{3\xi_j} \frac{3\xi_j}{3\xi_i} \right)} \right] [\chi'_{ij} + x_i \chi''_{ii} + x_j \chi'_{12}]$$

$$+ \left[\frac{x_j x_k \left(\frac{3\xi_j}{3\xi_k} \frac{3\xi_k}{3\xi_j} \right)}{x_j + x_k \left(\frac{3\xi_j}{3\xi_k} \frac{3\xi_k}{3\xi_j} \right)} \right] [\chi'_{jk} + x_j \chi'_{12}] \quad (16)$$

$$+ \left[\frac{x_i x_k \left(\frac{3\xi_i}{3\xi_k} \frac{3\xi_k}{3\xi_i} \right)}{x_i + x_k \left(\frac{3\xi_i}{3\xi_k} \frac{3\xi_k}{3\xi_i} \right)} \right] [\chi_k + x_i \chi''_{12} + x_k \chi'_{kk}]$$

For the investigated mixtures, if it is assumed that $\chi'_{ij} \cong \chi_{12}$; $\chi'_{ik} \cong \chi''_{12}$; $\chi'_{jk} \cong \chi'_{12}$; $\chi''_{ii} \cong \chi''_{kk} \cong \chi^*$, then Equation (16) can be written as

$$X^E = \sum_{i=1}^6 \Delta X_i = \left[\frac{x_i x_j \left(\frac{3\xi_i}{3\xi_j} \frac{3\xi_j}{3\xi_i} \right)}{x_i + x_j \left(\frac{3\xi_i}{3\xi_j} \frac{3\xi_j}{3\xi_i} \right)} \right] [(1+x_j)\chi'_{ij} + x_i \chi^*] + \left[\frac{x_j x_k \left(\frac{3\xi_j}{3\xi_k} \frac{3\xi_k}{3\xi_j} \right)}{x_j + x_k \left(\frac{3\xi_j}{3\xi_k} \frac{3\xi_k}{3\xi_j} \right)} \right] [(1+x_k)\chi'_{jk}]$$

$$+ \left[\frac{x_i x_k \left(\frac{3\xi_i}{3\xi_k} \frac{3\xi_k}{3\xi_i} \right)}{x_i + x_k \left(\frac{3\xi_i}{3\xi_k} \frac{3\xi_k}{3\xi_i} \right)} \right] [(1+x_i)\chi'_{ik} + x_k \chi^*] \quad (17)$$

Equation (17) contains four unknown parameters, χ^* , χ'_{ij} , χ'_{jk} and χ'_{ik} and we evaluated these parameters by employing the V^E_{ijk} and $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ data of the investigated ternary mixtures at four compositions. These parameters were then subsequently utilized to predict X^E ($X = V$ or κ_S) values at other values of x_i and x_j . Such predicted V^E_{ijk} and $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ values along with χ^* , χ'_{ij} etc. parameters are recorded in Tables II and III respectively.

Examination of Tables II and III reveals that predicted V^E_{ijk} and $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ compare well with their experimental values. This lends additional support to the assumptions made in deriving Equation (17). Even in those cases where agreement between experimental and calculated values is not good, the predicted values are of the same sign as the experimental values. This may be due to the presence of ternary i-j-k contacts which have not been presently considered.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, V^E_{ijk} and $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ values predicted by employing topology of the constituents of ternary mixtures have revealed that these V^E_{ijk} and $(\kappa_S^E)_{ijk}$ values compare well with their corresponding experimental values; where agreement between theoretical and experimental values is not impressive, the predicted values are of same sign.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Graovac, I. Gutman and N. Trinajstić, "Topological approach to the chemistry of conjugated molecules". New York: Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1977.
- [2] D.H. Rouvray, "Graph theory in Chemistry," R. Inst. Chem. Rev., vol. 4, pp. 173-195, 1971.
- [3] C. A. Coulson, "Notes on the secular determinant in molecular orbital theory". Proc Cambridge Phil. Soc., Vol. 46, pp. 202-206, 1950.
- [4] J.E. Dubois and A. Panaye, "Base-catalysed polyalkylation of aliphatic ketones. 1. Graph and topological description of reaction pathways," Tetrahedron Lett., vol. 10, pp. 1501-1504, 1969.
- [5] M. Randić, "Characterization of molecular branching," J. Am. Chem. Soc., vol. 97, pp. 6609-6615, 1975.
- [6] A.T. Balaban, Chemical applications of Graph theory. Academic Press, London, 1976.
- [7] H. Hosoya, "Topological index. A newly proposed quantity characterizing the topological nature of structural isomers of saturated hydrocarbons," Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn, vol. 44, pp. 2332-2339, 1971.
- [8] P.P. Singh, V.K. Sharma and S. P. Sharma, "Topological studies of the molecular species that characterize lower alkanol + methylene bromide mixtures : molar excess volumes and molar excess enthalpies," Thermochim. Acta, vol. 106, pp. 293-307, 1986.
- [9] P. P. Singh, R. K. Nigam, V. K. Sharma, S.P. Sharma and K.C. Singh, "Topological aspect of the excess enthalpies of binary mixtures of non-electrolytes," Thermochim. Acta, vol. 52, pp. 87-102, 1982.
- [10] P.P. Singh and V.K. Sharma, "Thermodynamics of ternary mixtures of non-electrolytes: excess volumes," Canad. J. Chem., vol. 61, pp. 2321-2328, 1983.
- [11] V.K. Sharma, Rajni and Romi, "Topological investigations in binary mixtures containing ether: molar excess volumes and molar excess enthalpies," Indian J. Chem., vol. 40A, pp. 1277-1281, 1968.
- [12] V.K. Sharma and S. Kumar, "Topological investigations of molecular interactions in mixtures containing 1,4-dioxane and alkanols," Thermochim. Acta, vol. 428, pp. 83-90, 2005.
- [13] Dimple, J.S. Yadav, K.C. Singh and V.K. Sharma, "Molecular interactions in binary mixtures containing 2-methylaniline," Thermochim. Acta, vol. 468, pp. 108-115, 2008.
- [14] V.K. Sharma and S. Kumar, "Excess isentropic compressibilities for 1,3-dioxolane or 1,4-dioxolane + water + formamide or N,N-dimethylformamide ternary mixtures at 308.15 K," J. Solution Chem., vol. 34, pp. 713-730, 2005.
- [15] K.C. Kalra, V.K. Sharma and A. Katoch, "Molar excess enthalpies of ternary mixtures containing nitrobenzene," Indian J. Chem., vol. 37A, pp. 393-398, 1998.
- [16] Dimple, J. S. Yadav, K. C. Singh and V. K. Sharma, "Molar excess volumes and excess isentropic compressibilities of ternary mixtures of o-Toluidine," J. Chem. Eng. Data, vol. 53, pp. 1935-1939, 2008.
- [17] J. A. Walmsley, E.J. Jacob and H.B. Thompson, "An investigation of the self-association of 2-pyrrolidinone in cyclohexane and carbon tetrachloride by means of spectroscopic and electric polarization measurements," J. Phys. Chem., vol. 80, pp. 2745-2753, 1976.
- [18] J.A. Walmsley, "Self-Association of 2-pyrrolidinone. 2. Spectral and dielectric polarization studies of benzene solutions," J. Phys. Chem., vol. 82, pp. 2031-2035, 1978.
- [19] J. Jadzyn, J. Malecki and C. Jadzyn, "Dielectric polarization of 2-pyrrolidinone-benzene solutions," J. Phys. Chem., vol. 82, pp. 2128-2130, 1978.
- [20] J.S. Yadav, Dimple and V.K. Sharma, "Topological investigations of thermodynamic properties of binary mixtures containing 2-pyrrolidinone, Thermochim. Acta, vol. 489, pp.45-52, 2008.
- [21] J. A. Riddick, W. B. Bunger and T. K. Sakano, Organic Solvents Physical properties and Methods of Purification. 4th Ed., Wiley, New York, 1986.
- [22] P.P. Singh and S.P. Sharma, "Molar excess volumes of ternary mixtures of non-electrolytes at 308.15 K," J. Chem. Eng. Data, vol. 30, pp. 477-479, 1985.
- [23] P.L. Pirlia-Honkanen and P.A. Ruostesuo, "Thermodynamic and spectroscopic properties of 2-pyrrolidinones. 1. Excess molar volumes of 2-pyrrolidinone + dichloromethane, + dimethylsulfoxide, + acetone, + 2-propanol," J. Chem. Eng. Data, vol. 32, pp. 303-306, 1987.
- [24] J. George and N.V. Sastry, "Densities, viscosities, speeds of sound, and relative permittivities for water + cyclic amides (2-pyrrolidinone, 1-

- methyl-2-pyrrolidinone, and 1-vinyl-2-propyl) at different temperature,” J. Chem. Eng. Data, vol. 49, pp. 235-242, 2004.
- [25] K. Tamura, S. Murakami and S. Doi, “Speeds of sound, densities, and isentropic compressibilities of {x-C₆H₁₂ + (1-x) C₆H₅CH₃, { x-C₆H₁₁ CH₃ + (1-x) C₆H₆}, and {x -C₆H₁₁ CH₃ + (1-x) C₆H₅CH₃} from 293.15 K to 303.15K,” J. Chem. Thermodyn., vol. 17, pp. 325-333, 1985.
- [26] C.M. Sehgal, B.R. Porter and J.F. Greenleaf, “Ultrasonic non-linear parameters and sound speed of Alcohol-Water mixture,” J. Acoust Soc. Am., vol. 79, pp. 566-570, 1986.
- [27] M. Dzida, A. Zak and S. Ernst, “Thermodynamic and acoustic properties of binary mixtures of alcohols and alkanes. 1. Speed of sound in (ethanol + n-heptane) under elevated pressures,” J. Chem. Thermodyn., vol. 37, pp. 405-414, 2005.
- [28] G.C. Benson and O. Kiyohara, “Evaluation of excess isentropic compressibilities and isochoric heat capacities,” J. Chem. Thermodyn., vol. 11, pp. 1061-1064, 1979.
- [29] R.C. Weast Ed., CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics, 68th ed., CRC Hand Press, Boca Raton: FL, 1987.
- [30] J.H. Hilderbrand, J.M. Prusnitz, R.L. Scott, Regular and related solutions, Van-nonstand Reinheld compound, New York, 1971.
- [31] J.S. Yadav, Dimple, V.K. Sharma, “Topological investigations of the molecular species and molecular interactions that characterize pyrrolidin-2-one + lower alkanol mixtures,” Thermochim. Acta, Available online April 2009 DOI:10.1016/j.tca.2009.03.014.
- [32] J.S. Yadav, “Excess thermodynamic functions and molecular interactions in multicomponent liquid mixtures,” Ph.D. Thesis, Dept. Chem., Maharshi Dayanand Univ., Rohtak, India, 2009.
- [33] M. L. Huggins, “The thermodynamic properties of liquids, including solutions I. Intermolecular energies in monoatomic liquids and their mixtures,” J. Phys. Chem., vol. 74, pp. 371-378, 1970.
- [34] M. L. Huggins, “The thermodynamic properties of liquids, including solutions Part 2. Polymer solutions considered as diatomic systems,” Polymer, vol. 12, 387-399, 1971.
- [35] P. P. Singh and M. Bhatia, Energetics of molecular interactions in binary mixtures of non-electrolytes containing a salt,” J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. I, vol. 85, 3807-3812, 1989.
- [36] P.P. Singh, R.K. Nigam, K.C. Singh and V.K. Sharma, “Topological aspects of the thermodynamics of binary mixtures of non-electrolytes,” Thermochim. Acta, vol. 46, pp. 175-191, 1981.

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